

A survey on Machine Learning for Life Sciences in Greece

BACKGROUND

The recent breakthroughs in Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning across all domains has highlighted the importance of these fields in research and innovation in Greece.

To further explore the emerging potential of AI in relation to the biosciences, the ELIXIR-GR Machine Learning group is seeking input from the community to help us map and better understand the landscape of AI within the biosciences. This survey is largely based on a similar effort run by [UKRI-BBSRC in 2021](#).

The questionnaire is covering the following overarching topics:

- Current landscape
- Opportunities and potentials
- People and talent
- Infrastructure

Artificial intelligence describes a suite of computational technologies and tools that aim to reproduce or surpass abilities of humans to undertake complex tasks like learning and problem solving, either with or without human intervention. For the purposes of this questionnaire, please consider AI as covering a wide spectrum of technologies with these capabilities that include, but are not limited to, approaches such as machine learning, deep learning, neural networks and other related technologies.

Responses from individuals, departments, HEIs, scientific societies, industry and other stakeholders with an interest in AI for the biosciences are welcomed. We would also particularly encourage responses from:

- Early career researchers
- Professional support staff
- Non-bioscience researchers working in related areas, such as mathematical and computational sciences

All information submitted will be treated in confidence. Non-attributable comments from the questionnaire responses may be used as part of subsequent activities.

The questionnaire contains 18 questions in total which should take approx. 10 minutes to fill in. The deadline for responses is **29 February 2024**. We thank you in advance for your time and input, and feel free to share this survey further. For any questions and/or comments, feel free to reach out directly to us (see contact details below).

Eleni Adamidi (ATHENA RC) eleni.adamidi@athenarc.gr

Alexandros Dimopoulos (BSRC AI. Fleming) dimopoulos@fleming.gr

Anastasia Krithara (NCSR Demokritos) akrithara@iit.demokritos.gr

Fotis Psomopoulos (INAB|CERTH) fpsom@certh.gr

Thanasis Vergoulis (ATHENA RC) vergoulis@athenarc.gr

Privacy Notice

Thank you for participating in our survey. Your privacy and the protection of your personal data are of utmost importance to us. This privacy notice aims to inform you about the collection, usage, and protection of your personal data in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The information you have provided for the machine learning for life sciences questionnaire will be collated and anonymised prior to analysis and will not be attributable to individuals.

Information gathered will be used by the ELIXIR-GR Machine Learning group, to:

- *Provide a dialogue that facilitates strategy development*
- *Contact you for follow up questions regarding your submission*
- *Contact you regarding future engagement opportunities*

If you do not agree to your data being used to this effect please let us know in your response (final question).

The personal data provided will be retained on our systems for as long as is required to carry out processing for the purposes outlined above. By providing your information you are consenting to its use as detailed above. Please note that your participation in this survey is entirely voluntary, and you are under no obligation to provide any personal data. However, without certain information, we may be unable to analyze the survey results accurately.

By participating in this survey, you acknowledge that you have read and understood this privacy notice and give your consent to the processing of your personal data as described herein.

* Indicates required question

Section on background

The following questions aim to capture the academic background, experience and status.

1. Which of the following most closely describes your position?

Mark only one oval.

- Head of Department / Centre Director/ R&D Director
- Chief Technology Officer/ Chief Scientific Officer
- Professor
- Research group leader
- Facility manager
- Technical Staff
- Bioinformatician, Data Scientist, or Research Software Engineer
- Research fellow
- Research & Development scientist / Postdoctoral researcher
- Engineer
- Student
- Other: _____

2. Who are you submitting this response on behalf of?

Mark only one oval.

- Myself
- My research group / team
- My department
- My organisation
- Other: _____

3. **What is the size of the research group you are active in:**

Mark only one oval.

1-5

6-20

21-50

More than 50

4. **What do you consider to be your broad area(s) of specialist knowledge? (select all that apply)**

Tick all that apply.

- Ageing
- Animal health
- Animal welfare
- Bioinformatics and computational biology
- Bioenergy
- Bioimaging
- Biomedicine
- Cell Biology
- Computer Science
- Crop science
- Diet and health
- Developmental biology
- Engineering
- Environmental science
- Evolutionary biology
- Immunology
- Industrial biotechnology
- Mathematical sciences
- Microbial food safety
- Microbiology
- Neuroscience and behaviour
- Pharmaceuticals
- Plant science
- Physics / biophysics
- Regenerative biology and tissue engineering
- Social science
- Software development
- Soil science
- Stem cells
- Structural biology
- Synthetic biology
- Systems biology (mathematical and/or computational modelling)
- Technology development (software and/or hardware)
- The 3 Rs (Replacement, Reduction and Refinement of animals in research)
- Other: _____

(Optional Section) In order to better understand and capture the diversity of responses, it would be helpful to get your input to the following questions:

5. Which best describes your gender?

 Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Transgender / Trans woman
- Transgender / Trans man
- Non binary
- Not listed
- Prefer not to say

6. Do you consider yourself to have a disability?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

AI/ML Landscape

The following questions aim to provide an overview of the AI/ML landscape in Greece, as perceived by you.

7. Please describe the data types and formats (e.g. image/tiff, sequencing/FASTQ, etc) that you are consistently using for your AI/ML solution (max 50 words)

8. Please list your three most recent/most important research outputs with ML/AI in Life Sciences (max 50 words)

9. Please describe your involvement in AI software / method development (max 50 words)

10. Please describe any training services on ML/AI for Life Sciences that you offer (max 50 words)

11. Please describe any AI/ML services you provision for Life Sciences (max 50 words)

12. In order of importance, what do you view as the current key challenges to delivering your AI-related research goals in Life Sciences? (max 50 words per answer)

13. **What current or future AI technologies from the following list (selected from within the ACM CCS ontology) below do you consider to be more impactful in changing the current biosciences research capabilities, or deliver fundamentally new ones?**

Tick all that apply.

- Natural language processing
- Knowledge representation and reasoning
- Computational control theory
- Cognitive science
- Multi-agent systems
- Intelligent agents
- Mobile agents
- Computer vision
- Supervised learning
- Unsupervised learning
- Reinforcement learning
- Multi-task learning
- Batch learning
- Online learning settings
- Active learning settings
- Semi-supervised learning settings
- Federated learning
- Classification and regression trees
- Kernel methods
- Neural networks
- Markov decision processes
- Ensemble methods
- Other: _____

14. If you are actively developing AI / ML methods for Life Sciences, from where do you obtain your compute capacity? Please indicate all that apply.

Tick all that apply.

- Local institutional resources
- National computational resources (such as ELIXIR-GR HYPATIA, GRNET ARIS)
- commercial cloud services
- Other: _____

15. Please briefly describe the technical infrastructure you are using (max 50 words).

16. Please rank the importance of the following statements towards identifying gaps (1-5, high to low) in supporting the use of AI in your field in Life Sciences.

Mark only one oval per row.

	1 high	2	3 medium	4	5 low
More early career researchers with interdisciplinary AI training, including bioscience-focused doctoral AI training	<input type="radio"/>				
More opportunities for continuing professional development in training on AI fundamentals available across career stages	<input type="radio"/>				
More training in data science aspects essential for enabling use of AI, available across career stages	<input type="radio"/>				
A specified ethics and regulation framework for AI/ML applications in Life Sciences	<input type="radio"/>				
More collaborative cross-discipline research projects	<input type="radio"/>				
Greater availability of technical professionals	<input type="radio"/>				

Greater level of support for using computational infrastructures

Greater level of support for embedding ML-operations within the lab

Greater interchange between academia and industry

Greater support for translation commercialization and dissemination for AI technologies

17. What are your key skills needs relating to AI? Which do you find are most challenging to recruit and/or retain? (maximum 50 words)

18. What types of activity would you like to see supported to promote more community-level discussions and activities for AI bioscience in Greece? What benefits could such activities provide? (max 200 words)

Thank you for your responses. If you'd like to receive feedback on the survey, please indicate your details below:

19. First name

20. Last name

21. Email

22. Organization

23. Department

24. **Would you be interested in receiving additional information/communications from this group?**

Mark only one oval.

Yes, I consent to receiving additional communications in the future

No, I'm not interested in receiving additional communications in the future
